

ISOTHERMAL CREEP RESPONSE OF AL-BASED MMCS UNDER TENSILE AND COMPRESSIVE LOADING

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SUMMARY: The isothermal creep response of various SiC reinforced powder-route Al-based composites were investigated at 270 and 300 °C in both tension and compression. In tension, microstructural damage was found to occur early during the deformation for large reinforcement size, in the form of cavities, preventing a true steady state from being reached. This was confirmed using instantaneous Poisson ratio measurement. The extent to which the damage dominated the tensile response was highly dependent on the reinforcement size. Minimum strain rates in tension were compared with strain rates in compression at similar composite strains. For 20 µm particulate reinforcement, strain rates during compression were lower than the minimum strain rates measured during tension. Creep resistance was found to increase with decreasing reinforcement size and increasing volume fraction in both tension and compression.

KEYWORDS: isothermal creep, tensile, compressive, damage, discontinuous, Al

INTRODUCTION

Although metal matrix composites have been acknowledged as attractive materials for a variety of aerospace and automotive applications for some while, relatively little research has been carried out to relate creep properties to specific microstructural parameters. Most of the work carried out to date has concentrated on the tensile response of the material [1-5], but in real situations the composite is likely to be subjected to a variety of stress states. In order for these materials to be utilised safely, it is essential to have a detailed knowledge of how they respond under combined thermal and mechanical loading situations. Previous workers have

also suggested that it is the load transfer effect which dominates the creep performance of such materials [1-3,6], however research on Al_2O_3 reinforced aluminium composites has suggested that in many cases it is the incidence and stability of damage which determines the creep response [7].

In the present research, an investigation was carried out on silicon carbide discontinuously reinforced aluminium composite containing different shapes and sizes of SiC. The isothermal creep response was then characterised under tensile and compressive loading. In both cases the damage mechanisms were characterised as a function of reinforcement parameters. In this way, a greater insight into the micromechanisms of damage and failure could be obtained, giving a better understanding of how these materials react in a wide variety of situations.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Material Preparation

Discontinuously reinforced commercially pure aluminium composite was produced using powder-blending followed by extrusion at 460°C , from billets with mean diameter of 170 mm down to rods of 7.5 mm radius. Reinforcements used were SiC particulates of $3\mu\text{m}$ (this material also contained $0.1\mu\text{m}$ SiC) and $20\mu\text{m}$. Composites were produced with volume fractions of 10 and 20% (referred to as 10/3_p 10/20_p etc.). Whisker reinforced material, at 10 vol.%, was also supplied by Risø National Laboratory, Denmark. In addition to these composites, unreinforced commercially pure Al was also prepared using the same powder-route procedure. All the composites contained approximately 0.8 vol.% of fine oxide platelets as a result of the processing route.

Mechanical Testing

Isothermal creep tests were then performed at 270°C and 300°C in tension. Compression creep tests were performed at 270°C on the $20\mu\text{m}$ particulate material. In the case of tensile deformation, the creep rig incorporated a twin elliptical infra-red furnace, the load train being placed at the focal line of the furnace. This allowed direct visual access to the specimen during deformation. Both the axial and transverse strains of the specimen could then be monitored simultaneously using scanning laser extensometry. The strain measurements were combined to obtain the instantaneous Poisson ratio. This enabled information about the processes of damage evolution to be obtained [7]. Local strain was monitored by marking some of the specimens with indentations of 0.08 mm depth at 2 mm intervals along the gauge length prior to testing and then measuring the diameter at these positions using the laser extensometer. After testing, the diameters were measured again and the distance between the indentations measured (to within $\pm 1\mu\text{m}$) using a travelling microscope.

Compressive creep tests were performed on an over-slung lever-type rig with a load transfer ratio of 10:1. The rig was modified for compression testing with self-aligning joints and compressive platens. The compressive platens held additional upper and lower fixtures made of high compressive strength and low thermal conductivity Zirconia supports for positioning the test specimen. Strain was measured using two linear vertical displacement transducers.

Microstructural Analysis

In order to reveal microstructural damage, specimens were sectioned and electropolished using Struers A2 electrolyte and Prolectol electropolisher. They were then examined using scanning electron microscopy. The grain structures were investigated by anodising the specimens at 20 V for 1 min using Barkers reagent (containing ~0.5% HBF₄) after careful mechanical polishing. The specimens were then examined using crossed polars. In all cases it was found that the grain structure was elongated in the extrusion direction. Results of as-fabricated grain sizes are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Average grain sizes of as-processed composites and unreinforced powder-route Al obtained from anodised specimens. Dimension are given relative to the composite extrusion direction.

Material	20/20 _p	20/10 _p	20/3 _p	10/3 _p	10 _w	MD105
Axial (µm)	29	40	12	19	80	75
Transverse (µm)	5.5	6.5	3	4	2.5	7

From Table 1 it can be seen that the composites consistently have significantly finer microstructures than the unreinforced Al matrix, with the grain aspect ratio for the whisker reinforced material being up to a factor of 5 greater than those of the particulate reinforced composites.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

General Tensile Creep Characteristics

The particulate reinforced composites were found to exhibit the majority of both the creep strain, and proportion of time to failure, in the tertiary regime. This is consistent with observations made on other discontinuously reinforced composite systems [7]. For the whisker reinforced material, primary creep took up a larger proportion of the creep life. This is illustrated by Fig. 1 which shows percentage of total strain spent in the three creep regimes for a range of creep tests. In all instances, an increase of temperature at constant load promoted a reduction in the fraction of the strain to failure spent in the primary and secondary regimes, and a correspondingly longer tertiary regime. This was generally more pronounced in the whisker reinforced material. When expressed as a proportion of the time to failure, the effect was somewhat less clear for the particulate materials, but followed a similar trend for the whisker system. The fact that tertiary creep essentially dominated the creep behaviour with the particulate reinforced composites suggests that damage is occurring early during the deformation.

Fig. 1: Percentage of strain spent in each creep regime for various composites, tested under tensile creep at either 270°C or 300°C.

Minimum strain rates and rupture times are given in Figs. 2 and 3. Several interesting effects can be seen from these data. It is evident that both the reinforcement aspect ratio and size have a strong influence on the creep resistance. On considering the 10 vol.% material, the higher aspect ratio whisker reinforcement clearly gives the best creep resistance. The 3 μm particulate shows an almost equally good response. However, the larger 20 μm reinforcement has significantly worse creep behaviour. This is due to several possible effects. Firstly, as the reinforcement size is increased, at constant volume fraction, so there will be an increase in the interparticle spacing. This influences the scale of the subgrain structure within the matrix, which has been shown to have a direct effect on the creep stress sensitivity. Another factor to be taken into account is that of damage. Microstructural observations have shown that the larger the scale of the reinforcement, the larger and hence less stable is the cavitation which occurs (the size of cavitation is directly related to the size of the reinforcement [8]). Consequently, in the 20 μm material, cavitation was large and unstable, leading to early failure. For the 3 μm reinforced material, there were many small cavities which were stable, resulting in a more highly creep resistant composite. This is consistent with observations that the larger the scale of damage within a composite, the more significant it becomes in determining the creep response rather than the degree of load transfer [7].

On considering the effect of volume fraction, these data show an interesting effect. For the small particulate reinforcement, increasing the volume fraction from 10 to 20% gives a corresponding increase in creep response. However, for the 20 μm material, there is very little difference between the behaviour at the two volume fractions. This suggests that the presence of this reinforcement is not resulting in efficient load transfer. This is confirmed by the fact that the unreinforced powder-route aluminium actually displays a better creep resistance than these composites. This is consistent with observations made on alumina particulate composites [7]. Neutron diffraction studies [9], using Bragg diffraction, have shown that under these conditions, there is very little load supported by the reinforcement. It was concluded that under certain experimental conditions there is a rapid rate of relaxation which essentially nullified the beneficial effects of load transfer to the reinforcement.

Fig. 2: Minimum strain rates as a function of initial applied stress for SiC composites tested in tension at 270°C, together with unreinforced powder-route aluminium.

Apparent Creep Exponent

The apparent creep stress exponent, n_{app} is defined by:

$$n_{app} = \left[\frac{\partial \ln \dot{\epsilon}}{\partial \ln \sigma} \right]_T = \frac{n\sigma}{\sigma - \sigma_o} \left(1 - \frac{\partial \sigma_o}{\partial \sigma} \right) \quad (1)$$

where $\dot{\epsilon}$ is the steady state strain rate, σ_o is the threshold stress (i.e. the stress below which creep rates are negligible) and n is the actual creep exponent. Values of the apparent creep exponent were calculated from the minimum strain rate/applied stress dependency for each of the materials under investigation. Mean values of the apparent exponent are presented in Table 2. The threshold stress, σ_o , was calculated from $\dot{\epsilon}^{1/n}$ vs. σ plots with forced values of true stress exponent, n , equal to 5 and 8. For these data, it was found that taking $n = 5$ gave better agreement with experimental data for the 20 μ m material than $n = 8$, which agreed with the findings of Park *et al.* [2]. In the case of the 3 μ m reinforcement, the available experimental data is not conclusive regarding this point.

Table 2: Average apparent creep exponents for various materials over stress ranges.

Material	T(°C)	σ (MPa)	Mean n_{app}	σ_o (MPa)	
				n=5	n=8
10% 20 μ m	270	39-46	16.6	29.6	21.9
20% 20 μ m	270	40-60	13.3	29.4	18.6
10% 3 μ m	270	54-64	30.5	48.5	42.8
20% 3 μ m	270	45-70	32.4	55.9	49.9

20% 3 μ m	300	62-71	30.1	54.8	48.6
10% w	270	50-58	37.5	46.7	42.6
10% w	300	40-47	18.2	37.9	29.3
Unrein. Al	270	39-47	14.8	28.6	19.8

From these data it can be seen that the apparent stress exponent increases with decreasing reinforcement size and increasing inclusion aspect ratio, but stays relatively constant for different reinforcement volume fractions.

Fig. 3: Failure times for SiC reinforced Al, together with unreinforced powder-route Al, under tensile loading at 270°C as a function of applied stress.

Poisson Ratio Measurement and Damage Evolution

Instantaneous Poisson ratio can give significant insight into the onset of damage processes, in the form of cavitation, during deformation. If plastic flow occurs, then the instantaneous Poisson ratio of the composite should be close to 0.5. If cavitation occurs within the composite, then an axial strain will be produced without a corresponding lateral contraction, resulting in a lowering of the instantaneous Poisson ratio.

Fig.5: Apparent creep exponent as a function of applied stress for 20% 20 μm and 20% 3 μm composite.

In-situ measurements of instantaneous Poisson ratio, taken during tensile creep are presented in Fig. 6 for selected particulate reinforced composites, together with the unreinforced Al. For all the composites tested, the instantaneous Poisson ratio dropped rapidly, early during the deformation, and then stabilised. This initial drop in the Poisson ratio is probably caused by factors which effectively increase the constrained region around each reinforcement particle during deformation. The fact that following the initial transitory behaviour, the rate of decrease of the Poisson ratio becomes approximately constant, suggests that the rate of matrix cavitation is constant during secondary creep. The instantaneous Poisson ratio data for the unreinforced powder-route Al remained close to 0.5 for the majority of the deformation.

It is also possible to obtain information regarding the effect of reinforcement size and volume fraction from these data. It can be seen that cavitation occurred more easily with higher volume fraction for both the reinforcement sizes investigated. This agreed with damage evolution trends observed during tensile deformation [8] and during eddy current monitoring [10]. This is consistent with the fact that an increase in volume fraction will result in an increase in the proportion of matrix which is effectively constrained and hence unable to deform plastically. It is also evident that cavitation levels are significantly higher with the larger reinforcement size. It should be noted that it is not appropriate to consider the Poisson ratio data once any localisation of the strain has occurred, but this technique does give valuable confirmation that damage processes occur very early in the creep process for these materials.

Fig. 6: Instantaneous Poisson ratio as a function of sample life for particulate reinforced composites during isothermal tensile creep at 270°C.

Comparison of Tensile and Compressive Behaviour

The relative rates of creep during tension and compression were obtained by comparing the strain rate in compression with the minimum strain rate measured in tension, at similar composite strains. Strain rates in tension and compression for the 20% 20 μm material are shown in Fig. 7. It can be seen from these data that the creep resistance in compression was consistently better than that in tension for the same material; the minimum strain rates in tension were found to be higher than corresponding rates observed in compression under the same initial load. Microstructural observations showed that in compression, the main form of damage was found to be reinforcement cracking (Fig. 8). There was some evidence of cavitation, but the incidence was significantly lower than in tension.

This behaviour is not unexpected, since it was the early and extensive cavitation which occurred during tensile loading which resulted in early tertiary creep behaviour. As this damage did not occur in compression, it was possible for a microstructural balance to build up, resulting in steady state behaviour. The fact that, as in tension, there was little difference between the 10 and 20 vol.% composites again suggests that load transfer does not occur effectively to this size of reinforcement at this temperature.

CONCLUSIONS

- At small reinforcement size, effective tensile creep resistance was obtained. The creep resistance was also found to increase with increasing aspect ratio.
- Larger 20 μm particulates were found not to reinforce the Al matrix effectively under these experimental conditions, and were in fact detrimental to the tensile creep resistance, relative to unreinforced material.

- High values of apparent stress exponent were observed. These increased with decreasing reinforcement size, and increasing aspect ratio.
- Poisson ratio measurement confirmed that damage occurred early and extensively under tensile loading, resulting in very early tertiary creep behaviour.
- In compression, strain rates were lower than corresponding minimum strain rates during tensile loading.

Fig. 7: Creep rates for 20% 20 μm Al crept at 270°C in compression(C) or tension (T), as a function of applied load.

Fig. 8: Micrograph of 10% 20 μm composite subjected to compressive creep at 270°C under an applied stress of 50 MPa. Note the extensive particle cracking.

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